

MEN4DEM

YOUTH WINGS AS CATALYSTS

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JUNE 2026

Funded by
the European Union

This report is published as part of the MEN4DEM project, which has received funding from the European Union under Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (grant number 101177356).

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To be cited as: Anlar, Brit (2026). Youth Wings as Catalysts. MEN4DEM Report.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.21060976

Authors: Brit Anlar is a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Amsterdam.

Acknowledgements: To Dr. Liza Mügge, Dr. Alexia Katsanidou, and Dr. Malin Holm for their feedback on early drafts of the report. Additionally, to the feedback from the Politics of Diversity group at the University of Amsterdam for their thoughts on the initial plan, design, and approach to the report.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project name	Masculinities for the Future of European democracy
Project acronym	MEN4DEM
Project number	101177356
Deliverable number	3.2
Deliverable name	Youth Wings as Catalysts
Due date	June 30, 2026
Submission date	June 30, 2026
Type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package	3
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.21060976

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Created by	Short Description of Version
1	19-05-2026	Brit Anlar	Draft version for internal review.
2	26-05-2026	Brit Anlar	Draft following editor review, for submission to internal reviewers.
3	23-06-2026	Brit Anlar	Draft following internal review.
4	29-06-2026	Brit Anlar	Final draft following editor's review.

MEN4DEM

ABOUT MEN4DEM

MEN4DEM (2025-2027) is an innovative collaborative co-creation project that involves six partner universities as well as a theatre group and a gender justice organization. The consortium studies various manifestations of masculinities in politics. Based on mixture of academic, activist, and artistic knowledge MEN4DEM will develop concrete tools to support democratic masculinities in Europe. The project was funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (grant number 101177356). The project website is: www.men4dem.eu.

LEAD BENEFICIARY

UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM

CONTRIBUTING BENEFICIARIES AND ASSOCIATED PARTNERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AfD	Alternative for Germany

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Political party youth wings connect youth social worlds to formal party power. They recruit and mobilize young people, represent youth claims, socialize members into political practice, support campaigns, communicate publicly, and create pathways into party roles, and elected office. This report focuses on two questions: How do youth wings exercise role and influence within party politics? Under what conditions can they operate as catalyst sites for democratic and anti-democratic masculinities?

The central claim is that youth wings shape which ways of doing politics become credible, desirable, and politically useful. It demonstrates that masculinities do not move only through explicit claims about men or gender, but they appear in everyday political practice: who gets invited, who speaks with authority, who gains status through loyalty and aggression, who performs care work, who receives protection, and which forms of conflict are rewarded.

The report uses a theory-informed evidence synthesis. Youth wing scholarship rarely studies masculinities directly; the report reads that literature through the scholarship on political masculinities, democratic socialization, political style, and normalization/mainstreaming. The evidence base combines rapid systematic review, thematic synthesis, a targeted conceptual review, and illustrative examples from the literature.

The systematic review demonstrates that youth wings are selective political spaces. Members are often already politically interested, civically active, highly educated, and in several studies, male. This selectivity gives youth wings particular significance as early sites where political opportunity, recognition, authority, and belonging are distributed.

Youth wings can cultivate democratic masculinities when they make care, equality, accountability, pluralism, solidarity, and non-violent disagreement part of political training. Campaign work can teach young members how to engage with citizens, active listening, and to treat public engagement as democratic responsibility. At the same time, youth wings can press parent parties on climate, equality, representation, and youth access, or open leadership pathways that value mentoring, coalition building, conflict mediation, and care-oriented organizing.

Youth wings may also, however, reproduce anti-democratic masculinities when they reward exhaustion, constant availability, factional aggression, insider loyalty, ridicule, and tolerate harassment and violence. Digital communication practices can amplify these

styles when humor, visibility, and conflict become detached from accountability mechanisms.

Parent parties shape how far youth wing ideas, styles, and practices travel. Youth wings may test claims, develop leadership styles, and socialize young activists, but parent parties decide whether these practices gain resources, visibility, policy attention, and/or public legitimacy. Parties that treat youth wings as campaign labor miss their democratic significance, while those that tolerate harmful practices risk giving anti-democratic masculinities legitimacy under the guise of youth politics.

The report identifies four points of action:

1. **Accountability**, for parent party actors: support youth wing autonomy while setting clearer democratic boundaries around harassment, discrimination, intimidation, anti-democratic rhetoric, and political violence.
2. **Safeguarding**, for youth-wing leaders: protect members' well-being and ensure safe, respectful participation through clear reporting channels, conflict procedures, anti-harassment norms, and care-oriented leadership.
3. **Inclusion**, for organizations that work with political parties (including training organizations and oversight bodies): widen access to youth wing participation and leadership pathways, especially for those young people who are less likely to be recruited, recognized, or supported.
4. **Communication**, for youth-wing leadership and parent party campaign teams: make campaign work and digital communication democratic, sustainable, and accountable, rather than extractive, abusive, or built around constant availability.

Youth wings strengthen democracy when they help young people learn care, accountability, pluralism, voice, and non-violent disagreement as a part of political life. They weaken democracy when they normalize hierarchy, aggression, and contempt for constraint. Parent parties, youth wing leaders, and oversight bodies can shape which path becomes more likely.

1. WHY YOUTH WINGS MATTER FOR DEMOCRATIC MASCULINITIES

Before young activists become party staffers, candidates, elected representatives, or senior party figures, where do they learn what kinds of authority, conflict, care, and belonging fit within democratic politics? This report analyzes political party youth wings as one answer to that question. It asks: How do youth wings exercise role and influence within party politics? Under what conditions can they operate as catalyst sites for democratic and anti-democratic masculinities?

Politics is learned before it is performed on a public stage, including how it is gendered. Democratic resilience rests on institutions, elections, laws, and formal party rules, and on the everyday settings in which young people learn what politics is supposed to feel like, sound like, reward, and permit. Families, schools, sports clubs, religious communities, online spaces, friendship groups, social movements, and local associations all teach lessons about gender, authority, belonging, leadership, conflict, care, loyalty, and participation. Across these settings, young people also learn who is taken seriously, which forms of confidence gain recognition, how disagreement is handled, and what kinds of political conduct seem possible.

Youth wings are especially relevant because they are party-linked socializing spaces that sit close to formal political power. They recruit and train young people, give them access to party networks, involve them in campaigns, and sometimes create pathways into party leadership, public office, and staff positions (Hooghe et al., 2004; Recchi, 1999). Youth wings teach young people how to practice politics (Malafaia et al., 2018). Their influence may be direct, as when they press parent parties on policy, representation, access to candidacies, or internal reform. It may also be indirect, such as shaping who enters party politics, what claims gain visibility, which political styles become normal, and which actors later move into staff, campaign, communication, candidate, or elected roles.

The report aligns with MEN4DEM's wider concern with spillover between grassroots, digital, and mainstream political spaces. It draws on scholarship on the manosphere, 'manfluencers,' political socialization, youth wings, and democratic masculinities to situate youth wings within a wider ecology of gendered political formation, while keeping its own claim bounded. The report does not show that youth wings reproduce manosphere cultures or directly import online misogyny into party politics. It explains why youth wings deserve attention as party-linked settings where gendered political scripts may be encountered, rejected, softened, translated, authorized, contested, or carried into political life.

The context is politically urgent. Young people are coming of age amid widening gender gaps in attitudes toward equality, the visibility of misogyny influencers and manosphere content, anti-gender campaigns, and growing receptivity to political styles that celebrate dominance, toughness, hierarchy, anti-feminism, and contempt for democratic constraint (Gottzén & Areschoug, 2025; Norris & Inglehart, 2019; Off et al., 2022). Research on the manosphere shows how digital spaces can organize male grievance through narratives of victimhood, status loss, sexual entitlement, anti-feminism, and hostility toward gender equality, while work on young masculinities cautions against treating these dynamics as a simple pipeline from online content to political extremism (Andersen, 2025; Botto & Gottzén, 2024; Ging, 2019; Gottzén & Areschoug, 2025).

Young people also encounter and create democratic alternatives, although these alternatives are often less visible online and less frequently theorized as democratic practice. In practitioner spaces connected to gender justice and men-and-masculinities work, boys and young men participate in peer-support platforms, youth education tools, fatherhood groups, anti-violence programs, and campaigns that link masculinity to care, pluralism, solidarity, and opposition to right-wing extremism (Besta et al., 2025; Schaaf & Mars, 2025). These practices resonate with research on democratic, caring, and inclusive masculinities, which shows how gendered identities can be reworked around empathy, equality, responsibility, and non-domination (Bjarnegård & Mügge, 2025; Wojnicka & de Boise, 2025).

Political masculinities provide the report's main analytical lens. Following Starck and Sauer (2014, p. 6), political masculinities refer to masculinities constructed around, ascribed to, or claimed by political actors. The concept directs attention to gendered ways of organizing authority, protection, hierarchy, care, conflict, loyalty, belonging, and democratic participation. The report uses masculinities in the plural because masculinities are not fixed traits of individual men, nor are they expressed only by men. Men, women, mixed-gender groups, organizations, and institutions can reproduce, soften, contest, or legitimize masculinized ways of doing politics. Anti-democratic masculinities refer to gendered practices and narratives that support hierarchy, exclusion, authoritarianism, hostility to gender equality, or the political acceptability of violence (Tomatis & Lomazzi, 2025). Democratic masculinities align masculine identities and practices with equality, pluralism, care, accountability, non-discrimination, and democratic participation (Bjarnegård & Mügge, 2025).

Socialization is central to this argument because masculinities and democratic norms are learned, practiced, and reworked over time. Youth wings operate at the meso-level: they

connect young people's peer worlds to formal political institutions, while creating their own routines, hierarchies, symbols, jokes, loyalties, and expectations.

Socialization refers to the continuing process through which individuals learn, negotiate, internalize, and reinterpret norms, values, behaviors, and expectations, including gender norms and democratic norms (Tomatis & Lomazzi, 2025). It happens through everyday interaction, through groups and institutions, and through wider social, legal, cultural, and political contexts.

Youth wings are not the only places where masculinities are learned. Sports clubs, for example, can shape young people's ideas about competition, teamwork, discipline, care, toughness, status, and peer recognition through repeated interaction, trusted adults, shared routines, peer accountability, and opportunities to practice different forms of leadership and care (Keddie, 2005, 2022; Sikweyiya et al., 2023). Youth wings share some of these features but add a direct connection to formal political activities such as campaigns, political debates, public speech, candidate pathways, and future political careers.

This direct connection to party politics makes youth wings especially relevant for understanding democratic resilience. Youth wings sit between several worlds at once: youth cultures, online spaces, activist scenes, schools, universities, workplaces, friendship groups, local communities, parent parties, party congresses, election campaigns, candidate pathways, and political leadership. In that position, youth wings can work as bridging institutions. They can bring young people into democratic politics, strengthen youth voices, cultivate inclusive leadership, and create spaces where young members practice care, accountability, pluralism, and democratic disagreement. They can also reproduce anti-democratic styles of political conduct when exclusionary norms, aggressive communication, anti-gender claims, harassment, or masculinized hierarchies are tolerated, rewarded, or left unnamed.

The central claim of this report is that youth wings can operate as catalyst sites. A catalyst site is not a single cause or a one-way pipeline. It is an organizational setting where political ideas, styles, emotions, and practices may be concentrated, reshaped, authorized, amplified, resisted, or carried into other arenas. Youth wings occupy this position because young members remain embedded in schools, universities, workplaces, friendship groups, activist scenes, online spaces, and local communities, while also gaining access to parent parties, campaigns, leadership networks, policy debates, public platforms, and future political careers.

Understanding youth wings as catalyst sites clarifies their role in processes of normalization and mainstreaming. Normalization refers to the erosion of stigma and the growing social acceptability of ideas, actors, styles, or practices; mainstreaming refers more specifically to the uptake, accommodation, or legitimation of previously niche or radical positions by mainstream political actors (Heinze & Off, 2026). Youth wings sit between these processes. They are close enough to peer and digital cultures to encounter claims, jokes, styles, and grievances that may be becoming familiar or socially acceptable, and close enough to parent parties to help make some of these claims, styles, and grievances politically usable, visible, contestable, or containable.

The report combines a rapid systematic review of youth-wing scholarship with conceptual work on political masculinities, political socialization, normalization and mainstreaming, and democratic transformation. The youth-wing scholarship shows what youth wings do: they mobilize, represent, socialize, campaign, communicate, and connect young people to parent-party politics. The conceptual literature helps explain why these functions matter for democratic and anti-democratic masculinities.

The report finds that youth wings are high-variance political spaces. In some contexts, they can support democratic participation, inclusive leadership, care-oriented political practice, and youth voice; in others, they may normalize exclusion, anti-gender claims, masculinized belonging, aggressive political styles, harassment tolerance, or parent-party deniability. The practical task is to identify what youth wings attract, what they socialize, which claims they authorize, how parent parties respond, and where democratic intervention becomes possible.

2. ANALYTICAL APPROACH: THEORY-INFORMED EVIDENCE SYNTHESIS

We use a theory-informed evidence synthesis to examine youth wings as possible catalyst sites for democratic and anti-democratic masculinities. The approach brings together two bodies of scholarship that rarely speak directly to one another. Youth-wing scholarship shows how these organizations recruit, mobilize, represent, socialize, campaign, communicate, and connect young people to parent-party politics, while scholarship on political masculinities, democratic socialization, norm translation, political style, and normalisation/mainstreaming explains why those organizational roles may matter for the development, circulation, contestation, or political uptake of democratic and anti-democratic masculinities.

Most youth-wing scholarship does not study masculinities directly with a few exceptions (see de Barros, 2022; Heinze, 2025; Malafaia et al., 2018). The existing literature gives rich evidence about youth wings as organizational spaces yet rarely asks how young members learn gendered expectations around authority, care, loyalty, hierarchy, conflict, protection, leadership, or belonging. We therefore use youth-wing scholarship to identify organizational roles and pathways, then read those findings through a conceptual framework focused on political masculinities and democratic socialization.

Four linked layers build the evidence base: a rapid systematic review, a thematic synthesis, a targeted conceptual review, and illustrative organizational examples from the reviewed literature. The systematic review identifies what youth wings do and how they are positioned in relation to parent parties. The thematic synthesis identifies recurring roles, relationships, and influence pathways across the corpus. The conceptual review supplies the vocabulary for interpreting these findings in relation to political masculinities. Illustrative examples show how the patterns identified in the review appear in concrete cases (see Table 1).

Table 1 Qualitative Method and Purpose

Qualitative method	Literature or Evidence Used	Purpose
Rapid systematic review	Scholarship on political party youth wings and closely related party linked youth organizations	Builds the empirical corpus and helps to identify what is known about youth wing roles, organizational positioning, and influence
Thematic synthesis	Article-level analytical memos prepared for studies included in the corpus	Synthesizes recurring patterns across the corpus, including organizational functions, autonomy, parent-party relationships, influence mechanisms, and ideological context
Targeted conceptual review	Academic literature on political socialization, norm diffusion and translation, mainstreaming, anti-gender politics, political masculinities, and political style	Provides the concepts used to interpret youth wings as possible catalyst sites for (anti)democratic masculinities
Illustrative organizational evidence	Examples reported within the reviewed youth-wing scholarship, including structures, practices, campaigns, communication, and pathways	Demonstrates how the patterns identified in the review appear in concrete cases

2.1 RAPID SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND THEMATIC SYNTHESIS

The rapid systematic review provides the empirical foundation for the report. Systematic reviews use explicit search, screening, and inclusion criteria to identify and synthesize existing research, and this review follows the reporting logic of PRISMA while adapting it to a rapid review design suited to the scale and policy timeline of the deliverable (Grant & Booth, 2009; Page et al., 2021; Thomas et al., 2013; Tricco et al., 2015).

A rapid review fits this corpus because youth-wing scholarship remains relatively small yet fragmented across political science, sociology, communication studies, anthropology, youth studies, and party politics. We searched Scopus and Web of Science Core Collection for publications from 2000 to 2025, combining terms such as 'youth wing,' 'youth section,' 'youth league,' 'party youth organization,' and 'young party members' with terms anchoring the search in party politics and intra-party organization.

We included studies when they treated formally affiliated political party youth wings, or closely related party-linked youth organizations, as a central unit of analysis. We also included studies that provided evidence on youth-wing roles, mobilization, membership,

representation, political socialization, campaign activities, public or digital communication, candidacy and leadership pathways, autonomy, ideological positioning, influence, or relationships with parent parties. We excluded studies focused on youth participation, voting behaviour, activism, or political attitudes without a clear connection to party-affiliated youth wings; studies of youth movements, student organizations, or civic organizations without formal party linkage; texts where youth wings appeared only peripherally; and non-scholarly sources.

We imported records into Rayyan for deduplication and screening. After deduplication, we screened 436 records by title and abstract, selected 78 full texts for further review, and included 60 studies in the final corpus (see Table 2). Backward and forward citation tracing supplemented the database search and helped address limitations in database indexing.

Table 2 Results from search and screening

Stage	Number of records
Records imported	709
Records after deduplication	436
Records screened by title and abstract	436
Records selected for full review	78
Final studies included in review	60

We analyzed the final corpus through a structured, framework-guided thematic synthesis. Five analytical dimensions guided the synthesis: organizational role or youth-wing function; institutional positioning and autonomy; influence mechanisms; youth-parent party relationships; and ideological context. For each included text, a structured analytical memo summarized the article’s relevance to the report, the youth wing or party-linked youth organization studied, its core findings, its organizational role, its institutional position, its relationship to the parent party, and any pathways of influence or mediation identified in the study.

Although we defined the main coding dimensions in advance, the synthesis allowed for inductive refinement. 'Campaign support,' for example, was refined to distinguish democratic campaign participation from extractive campaign labor or more coercive campaign auxiliary roles. 'Socialization' was refined to include formal political education, practical campaign learning, peer belonging, gendered role formation, leadership training, and political career preparation. 'Digital communication' emerged as a cross-cutting arena as several studies showed youth wings and party youth branches using social

media platforms, memes, visual messaging, and platform-specific styles to communicate party identity and mobilize young audiences.

The synthesis proceeded in two stages. We first mapped how existing scholarship represents youth wings: what they do, how they are institutionally positioned, how they relate to parent parties, and through what channels they may exercise influence. We then interpreted these empirical patterns through the targeted conceptual review on political masculinities, political socialization, norm translation, political style, and normalization/mainstreaming. The review did not assume catalyst mechanisms at the coding stage; instead, we developed those mechanisms analytically by connecting recurring patterns in the youth-wing literature to concepts from the conceptual review.

2.2 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

The conceptual review is organized around three concepts: political masculinities, political socialization, and the relationship between normalization and mainstreaming. Political masculinities identify gendered ideas and practices at stake. Political socialization locates youth wings within wider settings where young people learn shared expectations and unwritten rules about authority, care, conflict, hierarchy, loyalty, and belonging. Normalization and mainstreaming explain why youth wings matter for democratic politics: they sit between social worlds where ideas and styles can become familiar or acceptable and party arenas where some of those ideas and styles may gain recognition, strategic use, or political legitimacy.

Political masculinities provide the report's main analytical lens. Following Starck and Sauer (2014, p. 6), political masculinities refer to masculinities constructed around, ascribed to, or claimed by political actors. This definition moves the analysis beyond a narrow focus on men as individuals and toward the gendered ways in which political authority, protection, hierarchy, care, conflict, loyalty, and belonging become meaningful. Youth wings are important in this view because they are organizational settings where young people learn how to speak, campaign, lead, disagree, show commitment, manage conflict, build alliances, and claim political seriousness.

Gottzén and Areschoug's (2025) work on young masculinities and political subjectivities adds an important layer to this argument. Political subjectivities can be understood as the ways people come to see themselves, and are seen by others, as political actors. Rather than mirroring individual values or attitudes, they take shape through relationships, cultural expressions, identity categories, moments of conflict, and wider political conditions (Areschoug, 2022; Gottzén & Areschoug, 2025). This perspective is especially

useful for studying youth wings because young members adopt political positions while also learning what kind of political person they can become: a loyal party activist, a caring organizer, a combative debater, a future candidate, a defender of tradition, a critic of elites, a feminist ally, or an anti-feminist provocateur.

Ging's (2019) work on the manosphere helps specify one influential digital context in which anti-democratic masculinities now take shape. In this analysis, Ging demonstrates how older forms of antifeminist men's rights politics have been transformed by social media, where 'Red Pill' narratives, claims of male victimhood, anti-feminist grievance, and stories of humiliation or exclusion travel quickly across loosely connected online communities. These spaces are not unified movements with a single ideology, yet they can converge around hostility to feminism, resentment toward gender equality, suspicion of progressive politics, and the defense of male entitlement. The point for this report is broader than any one named type of masculinity: anti-democratic masculinities may operate through woundedness as well as dominance, turning loneliness, rejection, vulnerability, loss, or social displacement into resources for boundary-making, anti-feminist identification, and attacks on imagined enemies.

The report uses masculinities in the plural because masculinities are contextual, contested, and politically mobilized. Men, women, mixed-gender groups, organizations, and institutions can reproduce, soften, contest, or legitimize masculinized ways of doing politics. Anti-democratic masculinities refer to gendered practices and narratives that support hierarchy, exclusion, authoritarianism, hostility to gender equality, or the political acceptability of violence (Tomatis & Lomazzi, 2025, pp. 18–19) whereas democratic masculinities align masculine identities and practices with equality, pluralism, care, accountability, non-discrimination, and democratic participation (Bjarnegård & Mügge, 2025, pp. 9–17). This distinction keeps the analysis open to both harmful and democratic possibilities.

Political socialization provides the report's main process concept by locating youth wings within the wider settings where young people learn how gender and politics fit together. Drawing on the socialization scholarship synthesized by Tomatis and Lomazzi (2025), the report understands socialization as an ongoing process through which people learn, negotiate, internalize, and reinterpret norms, values, behaviors, and expectations, including gender norms and democratic norms (Döbler, 2026; Tomatis & Lomazzi, 2025). Young people arrive in youth wings already shaped by families, schools, peer groups, sports clubs, religious communities, media environments, online spaces, and national gender cultures, yet party-linked youth organizations can still redirect those earlier lessons

by placing them in settings where political conduct becomes practical, social, and consequential.

Youth wings are especially relevant for studying masculinities because gender socialization teaches young people what their social worlds expect from them as girls or boys, women or men, while approval, ridicule, recognition, exclusion, and other forms of social control give those expectations force (Lomazzi, 2023; Wharton, 2026). Keddie's (2005, 2022) work on boys and peer culture shows how these expectations can take shape through competition, bravado, alliance-building, sporting cultures, humor, physical toughness, denigration, and the search for status among peers. Such dynamics are not confined to childhood or sport. In party youth wings, peer recognition, loyalty, endurance, confidence, rivalry, humor, and access to senior actors can become political lessons about who belongs, who leads, who appears serious, and which forms of masculinity gain organizational value.

Youth wings therefore occupy a significant point in the socialization process. They gather young people at a moment when earlier lessons about authority, care, competition, conflict, belonging, and recognition meet the practical demands of party politics. Through meetings, campaigns, debates, training sessions, leadership contests, social events, digital communication, parent-party encounters, and internal conflict, young members learn how political authority is performed, whose labor counts, how disagreement is handled, which forms of confidence receive recognition, and what kinds of conduct open future opportunities (de Roon, 2022; Malafaia et al., 2018). These lessons can cultivate democratic capacities such as care, pluralism, accountability, non-violent disagreement, and shared responsibility, or they can reproduce hierarchy, exclusion, leader loyalty, harassment tolerance, anti-feminism, and aggression as signs of political strength.

Heinze and Off's (2026) distinction between normalization and mainstreaming provides the main anchor for understanding how youth-wing practices may move toward formal politics. Normalization refers to broader shifts in social norms and public discourse, including the erosion of stigma and the growing social acceptability of ideas, actors, styles, or practices. Mainstreaming refers more specifically to the uptake, accommodation, or legitimation of previously niche or radical positions by mainstream political actors (Heinze & Off, 2026, pp. 6–8). This distinction is useful because youth wings sit between peer, digital, activist, and youth cultural settings where ideas and styles may become familiar, and political party arenas where some of those ideas and styles may become politically usable.

This framework helps the report avoid a one-directional account of political influence. Youth wings do not merely transmit ideas from online or grassroots spaces into parent parties. They participate in exchanges between online, grassroots, youth, and party settings, where ideas and styles may be softened, sharpened, contested, ignored, amplified, disciplined, or repackaged. In practice, an informal joke, grievance, slogan, or style of confrontation can become a campaign strategy, organizational message, policy frame, leadership norm, or marker of political credibility. Youth wings provide party-linked organizational settings where these changes can happen close to formal politics.

The distinction between normalization and mainstreaming also clarifies the role of parent parties. Youth wings may test claims, styles, and emotional appeals, but parent parties shape whether those claims and styles travel further. Senior party actors may adopt, soften, ignore, discipline, instrumentalize, or distance themselves from youth-wing practices. They may treat youth wings as democratic schools, sources of youth voice, campaign labor, ideological pressure, reputational risk, or spaces where more controversial or aggressive political styles can appear without directly implicating the main party (Seeberg, 2025). The democratic stakes therefore lie in what youth wings say and do, and in how parent parties respond when youth-wing practices approach the mainstream.

2.3 FROM YOUTH-WING ROLES TO CATALYST MECHANISMS

The catalyst-site framework synthesizes the systematic review and conceptual review to answer the deliverable's role-and-influence question. It does not claim that youth-wing scholarship already names youth wings as catalyst sites for political masculinities, since most of that literature does not study masculinities directly. The framework emerges by reading youth-wing roles through concepts that explain how political ideas, styles, emotions, norms, and practices move across social and institutional settings. The systematic review identifies youth-wing roles and pathways of influence, while the conceptual review explains why those roles may matter for the socialization, authorization, movement, normalisation, filtering, or contestation of democratic and anti-democratic masculinities (see Table 3).

Table 3 From youth-wing roles to catalyst mechanisms

Review finding	Conceptual link	Catalyst mechanism	Relevance for Political Masculinities
Youth wings mobilize young people selectively into party-linked spaces.	Political socialization; youth participation; political masculinities.	Selective attraction and sorting.	Youth wings may attract, invite, and sort young actors through democratic commitments, solidarity, care, grievance, protection, anti-establishment style, recognition, or belonging.
Youth wings represent youth coded claims in party and public arenas.	Representative claim-making; political masculinities; normalization and mainstreaming.	Authorization and translation.	Youth wing affiliation can give selected claims about equality, care, protection, hierarchy, anti-feminism, grievance, or democratic disagreement party-adjacent legitimacy.
Youth wings socialize members through training, meetings, campaigning, friendship, hierarchy, and peer recognition.	Meso-level socialization; gender norms; democratic and anti-democratic masculinities.	Rehearsal and normalization of political conduct.	Members learn what forms of authority, care, conflict, loyalty, humor, endurance, and leadership are admired, tolerated, rewarded, or rejected.
Youth wings campaign, communicate digitally, use public styles, and create leadership/candidate pathways.	Political style; digital communication; normalization and mainstreaming.	Amplification and transmission.	Political masculinities become visible and portable through slogans, memes, debate styles, campaign labor, public speeches, and leadership pathways.
Youth wings relate to parent parties through influence, conflict, responsiveness, discipline, neglect, or instrumentalization.	Party organization; mainstreaming; parent-party responsiveness.	Filtering, containment, uptake, deniability.	Parent parties may adopt, soften, ignore, discipline, instrumentalize, or distance themselves from youth wing repertoire, shaping whether and how they travel into mainstream politics.

These mechanisms clarify what the catalyst-site concept adds: youth wings become analytically relevant when their ordinary party roles give political masculinities organizational form, drawing selected young actors into party-linked networks, giving some claims and speakers party-adjacent credibility, teaching members what conduct

gains reward, making ideas, styles, and practices visible and portable through campaigns and communication, and leaving parent parties to shape whether those ideas, styles, and practices are taken up, blocked, softened, ignored, or disowned.

The framework also moves away from a pipeline model by treating political masculinities as ideas, styles, and practices that move unevenly across settings and change form as they travel: a grievance may become a slogan, a joke may become a campaign style, a protection claim may become a policy frame, a caring practice may become a leadership norm, and a confrontational debate style may become a marker of political seriousness. Youth wings provide party-linked settings where these transformations can happen close to formal politics.

To those ends, this framework supports the study of spillover by treating youth wings as high-variance organizations rather than democratic solutions or democratic threats. In some settings, youth wings may help cultivate democratic masculinities by rewarding care, accountability, pluralism, non-violent disagreement, solidarity, and shared responsibility; in others, they may help normalize anti-democratic masculinities by rewarding hierarchy, grievance, aggression, anti-feminism, leader loyalty, harassment tolerance, or contempt for democratic constraint. The empirical question is what youth wings attract, authorize, rehearse, amplify, and filter, and how parent parties respond when those ideas, styles, and practices enter party-linked political life.

3. FINDINGS: YOUTH WING ROLES AS CATALYST MECHANISMS

The systematic review identifies three recurring roles through which youth wings matter within party politics: they mobilize young people into party-linked activity, represent youth-coded claims, and socialize young political actors, while campaigns, digital communication, candidate pathways, and leadership development appear across the corpus as cross-cutting arenas where these roles become visible in practice (de Roon, 2022). Building on the framework developed in Section 2, this section applies the catalyst-site lens to those findings.

Because youth-wing literature rarely studies democratic or anti-democratic masculinities directly, its value lies in showing where political masculinities may be learned, authorized, circulated, filtered, or contested. Youth wings draw selected young people into party-linked spaces, give some youth-coded claims, organizational voice, teach young members how politics is practiced, and use campaigns, communication, and leadership pathways to make some ideas, styles, and practices visible and portable. Viewed through the framework developed above, these roles become catalyst mechanisms: selective attraction and sorting; authorization and translation; rehearsal and normalization of political conduct; and amplification and transmission.

3.1 MOBILIZATION AS SELECTIVE ATTRACTION AND SORTING

Mobilization is the first way youth wings can operate as a catalyst site for political masculinities. This section focuses on who youth wings attract into party-linked spaces, why these spaces feel politically and socially meaningful, and how selective recruitment shapes the masculinities that become available, recognizable, and rewarded in early party life. The core argument is that mobilization sorts and concentrates certain young actors, claims, ambitions, grievances, care commitments, and styles of belonging into formal political institutions.

Youth wings' mobilizing function refers to their capacity to draw adolescents and young adults into organized party activity. The review shows that this function reaches beyond recruitment: youth wings create youth-specific entry points into party life, activate young people through campaigns and events, provide peer-based political communities, and open early pathways into activism, staffing, leadership, candidacy, and public office (Cross & Young, 2008; de Roon, 2022; Hooghe et al., 2004; McDonnell et al., 2025). Mobilization works organizationally and socially, connecting young people to formal party

structures while politicizing them in the peer environments where they study, work, socialize, joke, argue, and form political identities (Gordon & Taft, 2011).

From the perspective of political masculinities, mobilization shapes who moves toward party-linked youth spaces and why those spaces feel attractive. Bolin and Jungar's (2024) study of Swedish youth wing members makes this social dimension concrete: youth wing members described youth wings as communities of shared values, political discussion, and friendship while also identifying tensions around parent-party expectations, campaign work, careerism, conflict, and factionalism. The idea that youth wings are places for "people like me" can refer to age, ideology, class, education, race, region, gender, sexuality, or imagined political futures. To those ends, youth wings can invite young people into democratic commitments, care, equality, and political voice, or into narrower forms of belonging built around anti-establishment rebellion, nationalist protection, resentment toward elites, or the pressure of a combative peer community.

The review also shows that youth wings are institutionally widespread, even where their membership bases remain small. Allern and Verge (2017, p. 119) find that roughly 80 percent of parties in the Global North maintain a youth wing, making youth wings the most common formal party-linked auxiliary organizations. The Dutch case, however, demonstrates that this institutional presence should not be confused with broad youth mobilization into party politics. De Roon (2022) finds that Dutch youth wing membership grew tremendously in the 2000s and 2010s but still less than one percent of all Dutch young people between 14-27 years of age belong to one of the youth wings she explored. Youth wings may therefore remain organizationally resilient, and in some cases grow, without reaching young people at scale. Their influence, then, lies less in mass recruitment than in the concentration of politically active young people near party institutions.

Selectivity is one of the most important findings of the review. Rather than mobilizing youth as a broad demographic category, youth wings often gather a distinctive subset of young people. De Roon (2022) finds that Dutch youth-wing members are more likely than the wider youth population to be male, older within the youth category, urban, and enrolled in higher education. Spanish research similarly finds that party youth-wing members tend to be men, highly educated, civically active, and politically ambitious, with comparable patterns documented across youth wings in Australia, Austria, Germany, Italy, and Sweden (Alarcón-González, 2017, 2021; McDonnell et al., 2025). Despite often being male dominated, this finding does not reduce youth-wing politics to male dominance; research on populist radical right party activism shows that women can be highly active in parties often described as 'men's parties' when party networks create routes into

participation and recognition (Ammassari, 2026). The stronger point is that youth-wing mobilization is socially patterned, shaping which young actors enter party-linked spaces, which ambitions gain recognition, and which forms of belonging become available.

Mobilization also works through invitation and organizational availability. Cross and Young's (2008) study of young Canadian Liberal Party members shows that youth-wing membership strongly associates with higher levels of party activism, while Sebestyen's (2020) study of Hungarian students shows that being asked by a party organization to participate ranks among the strongest predictors of party engagement. Invitation can support democratic inclusion when it broadens access and builds confidence among young people who might otherwise remain outside party politics. Yet, it can also reproduce exclusion when invitations travel through informal networks, elite educational spaces, homosocial friendships, or activist circles where toughness, availability, humour, and insider loyalty already operate as tests of belonging.

Once young people enter youth-wing spaces, mobilization can become a pathway into political recognition. Members may become campaigners, board members, staffers, candidates, elected representatives, or party officers. Earlier scholarship emphasized youth wings' recruitment and training functions, while more recent studies show how youth-wing participation can shape political ambition, career expectations, and access to electoral politics (Ammassari et al., 2023; Bolin et al., 2023; Hooghe et al., 2004; Jalali et al., 2024). These pathways may reward democratic forms of participation, care, pluralism, and shared responsibility, or more exclusionary forms of recognition such as the tireless campaigner, the loyal insider, the strategic networker, the fearless provocateur, or the young actor able to withstand pressure, ridicule, and hierarchy.

Youth-wing members remain embedded in wider youth social worlds as students, classmates, teammates, colleagues, friends, and online participants as well as party activists. Youth-wing mobilization may therefore have effects beyond formal party boundaries, as members carry partisan language, campaign practices, ideological cues, political humour, gendered styles of debate, and ideas about leadership or authority into classrooms, group chats, sports clubs, student associations, workplaces, and online communities. This movement does not create a pipeline from youth wings to wider youth culture or from youth culture to parent parties, but it positions youth-wing members as carriers of political ideas and practices across several social and institutional settings.

Mobilization works as a catalyst mechanism because it attracts, invites, sorts, and concentrates selected young actors near party institutions while those actors remain embedded in wider youth social worlds. Through the grievances, solidarities, ambitions,

and styles of belonging that make some youth wings attractive, mobilization can give democratic or anti-democratic masculinities a route into organized political life.

Democratic masculinities become more likely when mobilization widens access, supports voice, values care, and gives young people real responsibility. Anti-democratic masculinities become more likely when mobilization rewards hierarchy, exclusion, endurance, aggression, or insider loyalty as the price of political belonging.

3.2 REPRESENTATION AS AUTHORIZATION AND TRANSLATION

Representation is the second way youth wings can act as catalyst sites for political masculinities. This section asks which youth-coded claims youth wings make politically credible, which young actors are authorized to speak, and how parent parties respond when youth wing claims move toward formal party arenas. The core argument is that representation is not only about whether youth wings “speak for youth”. It is also about authorization and translation: youth wings can turn selected concerns, identities, emotions and styles of political voice into party-facing claims.

Youth wings also perform a representative function when they articulate youth-specific or generational concerns, channel them into party structures, and make claims on behalf of young party members in public and intra-party arenas (de Roon, 2022). This role can include developing political programmes, participating in party congresses, lobbying senior party actors, issuing public statements, engaging with media, supporting young candidates, and pressing parent parties to adopt positions that youth-wing members identify as urgent. Representation therefore involves claim-making, agenda-setting, and the translation of youth concerns into party language and institutional demands (de Roon, 2022; Saward, 2006).

From the perspective of political masculinities, representation matters because youth wings help make some speakers, claims, and styles politically credible. A young person who makes a claim in a friendship group or digital space is often speaking from one position, while a youth-wing chair, board member, or candidate, speaks from another. Youth wing affiliation, therefore, can give claims borrowed party legitimacy even when those claims remain contested within the parent party. To those ends, representation can authorize gendered ways of doing politics that support care, equality, and democratic disagreement, or grievance, hierarchy, and contempt for compromise.

Youth wings occupy an intermediate position within party organization. They are not external civil society organizations, yet they also retain a youth-specific identity that may differ from senior party actors. This position gives them proximity to party elites,

congresses, programmes, and candidate-selection processes while allowing them to articulate claims shaped by generational experience. Young people remain structurally underrepresented in parliaments, cabinets, candidacies, and party leadership, which limits their direct influence on formal policymaking and agenda-setting (Kurz & Anlar, 2026; Stockemer & Sundström, 2022). Youth wings cannot solve youth underrepresentation on their own, but they can create institutional channels through which young members claim a place in party deliberation.

The reviewed literature offers several examples of youth-wing representation. In the Netherlands, youth-wing chairs from ten parties signed a joint climate manifesto before the 2017 parliamentary election, translating sustainability concerns into demands for the post-election coalition agreement (de Roon 2022). In Norway, youth wings helped advance gender-neutral conscription by framing it through equality, civic duty, and generational change, while in Germany, youth organizations within the Social Democratic Party, the Free Democratic Party, and Alliance 90/The Greens helped keep cannabis legalization on the agenda through internal pressure and campaign messaging (Hassenkamp et al., 2023; Tresse, 2013; Unge Høyre, 2008). These cases show youth wings translating youth-coded concerns into organized pressure, party debate, and public claims.

Representation can move in democratic or anti-democratic directions, depending on party family, organizational autonomy, ideological context, and parent-party response. Research on populist radical right youth leaders in Austria and Germany demonstrates that young party actors may formally recognize democratic principles while advancing more majoritarian and anti-egalitarian understandings of democracy, particularly around minority rights, inclusive citizenship, protest, and executive authority (Anter et al., 2025). This is not the same process as democratic representation. Democratic representation authorizes care, equality, pluralism, and accountability as youth political concerns. Anti-democratic representation authorizes hierarchy, exclusion, protectionist nationalism, anti-egalitarian citizenship, or contempt for constraints on majority rule as youth political voice.

Heinze's (2025) work on the Young Alternative for Germany similarly shows how a far-right youth organization can operate as a recruitment site, ideological pressure actor, and radicalizing infrastructure within the broader party environment. The Young Alternative was officially recognized as the Alternative for Germany's (AfD) youth wing in 2015, gained formal participation rights, and later developed more openly radical positions, including through the 2018 Deutschlandplan (*Plan for Germany*), which prioritized the cultural and ethnic preservation of the German people and proposed restrictive asylum measures. Heinze also shows that youth-wing policy debates could travel into broader AfD

debates, including on pension policy, and that the relationship between the youth wing and parent party involved both distancing and continued institutional connection (Heinze, 2025). Heinze's work demonstrates that youth-wing representation can give radicalized gendered and nationalist claims organizational form, party access, and a route toward wider political uptake.

Parent-party responsiveness shapes whether youth-wing representation travels further. Bolin (2025) shows that Swedish youth wing members often understand their organization as a vehicle for influencing the parent party rather than as a support structure for senior party decisions. Seeberg (2025) shifts attention to the other side of the relationship, showing that youth wing representation depends on whether senior party actors treat youth wing claims as relevant, legitimate, or strategically useful. Candidate selection adds another layer to this relationship as youth wings may lobby, nominate, endorse, or mobilize support for young candidates while senior party selectors retain control over list placement, electable positions, and access to office (Hazan & Rahat, 2010; Jalali et al., 2024; Kurz & Ettensperger, 2024).

Representation therefore works substantively and organizationally. Substantively, youth wings articulate positions on climate, equality, conscription, drug policy, youth inclusion, democracy, gender, or national belonging. Organizationally, they speak from inside the party institution, with access to congresses, committees, campaign channels, candidate pathways, and senior actors. From the perspective of political masculinities, representation is therefore also about authorization: which claims about care, protection, family, nation, equality, grievance, or hierarchy become recognizable as youth political concerns; which speakers receive serious attention; and which styles of political voice gain reward, whether conciliatory, combative, solidaristic, provocative, managerial, caring, or protective.

Ultimately, representation becomes a catalyst mechanism when youth wings translate selected concerns and values into party-facing claims. That translation may support democratic masculinities when youth wings authorize care, equality, accountability, pluralism, and non-violent disagreement as credible political positions; it may support anti-democratic masculinities when youth wings authorize grievance, dominance, anti-feminism, hierarchy, or protectionist claims as the voice of young people. In both cases, representation gives some gendered ideas and styles party-adjacent legitimacy while leaving others unheard, softened, disciplined, or excluded.

3.3 SOCIALIZATION AS REHEARSAL AND NORMALIZATION OF POLITICAL CONDUCT

Socialization is the third and most direct way youth wings can operate as catalyst sites for political masculinities. This section asks what young members learn through participation, which gendered expectations become attached to political seriousness, and how youth-wing cultures shape the forms of authority, care, conflict, loyalty, endurance, and belonging that young actors may carry forward. The core argument is that socialization does more than transmit party knowledge or political skills. It gives politics an everyday form, teaching young members what politics feels like, what it rewards, what it tolerates, and which democratic or anti-democratic masculinities become credible in organized party life.

The youth-wing literature has long treated political socialization as one of the central functions of party youth organizations (de Roon, 2022; Hooghe et al., 2004). Youth wings provide formal and informal settings where young members acquire political knowledge, learn party ideology, develop practical skills, build networks, and gain experience in campaign work, public communication, internal debate, and organizational leadership. They also teach members how to navigate the unwritten rules of party life: when to speak, whom to approach, how to build alliances, how to disagree without losing access, how to show loyalty, and how to position oneself as a credible political actor (Anlar, 2026).

Ethnographic work from within youth wings makes these everyday lessons visible. Malafaia et al.'s (2018) study of a Portuguese youth wing, conducted around the 2015 parliamentary election, shows young activists learning politics through campaigning, debate, internal meetings, friendship, hierarchy, public interaction, exhaustion, and conflict management. Campaigning was not treated only as leaflet distribution. One member explained that giving a pamphlet to someone was an excuse to talk and debate with the person receiving it. Another senior member described the youth wing's campaign style as "pedagogical": members were expected to speak with citizens, explain proposals, provide information, and rebuild trust in institutional politics through proximity and public explanation (Malafaia et al., 2018). These examples show youth-wing socialization as practice-based learning: young members learn politics by doing politics in public.

This learning also took place inside the organization. Malafaia et al. (2018) further describe youth-wing meetings where members debated institutional questions, discussed how government should be formed, and linked those debates to the need for political education in schools and among citizens. They also describe a proposed training camp for youth-wing members that would include critical thinking, public communication, teamwork, and political marketing (Malafaia et al., 2018). Campusano's (2019) study of youth militancy in

party-political organizations in Argentina reinforces this point in another context. In their work, they demonstrate how young activists are formed through training, mentorship, municipal work, territorial activity, and gradual incorporation into party identity and hierarchy. Across these studies, politics is taught as embodied routine. Young members are taught how to speak, organize, debate, represent, show loyalty, contest decisions, and belong politically.

Organizational culture shapes the democratic quality of this learning. Malafaia et al. (2018) show that youth-wing participation can generate democratic learning, political efficacy, communication skills, critical thinking, and a sense of politics as collective work oriented toward the public good. The pamphlet example is useful precisely because it shows a democratic version of political socialization where campaigning becomes a lesson in public explanation, listening, persuasion, and responsibility to citizens. From the perspective of political masculinities, this supports democratic masculinities when young members learn authority through care, accountability, proximity, communication, and public service rather than domination or contempt.

The same ethnography also shows the more demanding side of youth-wing socialization. Malafaia et al. (2018) also describe a culture in which political success required mobilization capacity, instrumental relationships, being present, and placing politics above health. One member framed electoral struggle through sacrifice and insisted that the youth wing could not abandon the campaign on its final day. These examples do not make the youth wing anti-democratic, but they do show how organizational learning can reward endurance, constant availability, sacrifice, and toughness. From the perspective of political masculinities, this is the double edge of socialization. The same campaign that teaches public engagement can also teach young members that political seriousness requires exhaustion, pressure, and the ability to withstand personal costs.

Ideological formation also forms part of socialization. Youth wings teach members how to interpret political conflict, imagine collective identity, and understand the boundaries of legitimate disagreement. Jaraisy and Agbaria's (2024) work on the Young Communist League in Israel shows how party-linked youth organizations can support political education, identity formation, and empowerment while generating tensions around ideology, belonging, and collective identity. Kolltveit and Karlsen's (2026) Norwegian study shows that youth-wing elites may act as ideological correctives or policy laboratories, often taking more issue-distinctive or radical positions than parliamentary candidates and voters, especially on generational issues such as climate. McDonnell et al. (2025) further show that youth-wing members include radicals, moderates, and aligned members whose

positions vary by party family, membership length, and career ambition. To those ends, youth wings socialize young actors into political positions, but not in a single direction.

The Young Alternative for Germany shows the riskier version of ideological socialization. Heinze's (2025) analysis shows that the youth wing did not only train young members in party routines but that it also helped create networks, form young cadres, articulate more radical positions, and connect youth-wing development to broader AfD radicalization. The Young Alternative's early radicalization, contacts with far-right groups, internal "trench warfare," and later the 2018 Deutschlandplan (*Plan for Germany*) show how youth-wing socialization can give exclusionary and nationalist claims organizational form. This case does not stand for all youth wings, but it makes the anti-democratic pathway concrete. Youth-wing socialization can train actors, claims, and styles that later become more visible inside formal party politics.

Peer belonging gives socialization its emotional force. Youth wings are political organizations and social worlds built through friendship, recognition, shared labour, humour, loyalty, and attachment. Members learn who counts as politically serious, who earns trust, who leads, and what forms of commitment gain reward. De Barros' (2022) study of Brazilian party youth groups describes them as "schools of politics," while showing that these schools can be gendered. Male members invoked *brodagem*, or brotherhood, as a form of political belonging linked to male bonding, hegemonic masculinities, and the reproduction of politics as a male-coded domain. Peer belonging can therefore support political confidence and collective identity, while also creating insiders and outsiders.

The youth-wing literature rarely studies democratic or anti-democratic masculinities directly, but it identifies organizational conditions through which young people may learn, reproduce, soften, or contest gendered political norms. Male-dominated membership, informal peer recognition, intensive campaign labour, loyalty expectations, hierarchical advancement, and expectations of toughness, endurance, and constant availability can shape who feels entitled to speak, lead, endure, care, and belong. Although Malafaia et al. (2018) do not analyze masculinities directly, their account of a mostly male youth-wing setting raises gendered questions about voice, leadership, exhaustion, and rewarded forms of assertiveness. De Barros (2022) makes this gendered dynamic even more explicit, showing how political belonging can be coded through brotherhood and male-coded sociability.

Ultimately, then, youth wings do not socialize all members in the same direction, and they do not automatically produce parent-party loyalty, elite ambition, or democratic commitment. When taken together, these findings from various youth wing studies sharpen

the argument that youth-wing socialization is relational, uneven, and conditional on organizational experience.

Socialization works as a catalyst mechanism when youth wings give political masculinities everyday form. They can teach deliberation, participation, public responsibility, pluralism, communication, and political efficacy, and they can reproduce hierarchy, exclusion, brotherhood, careerism, deference, exhaustion, or aggressive political conduct. The outcome depends on conditions identified across the review: youth-wing autonomy, openness of internal deliberation, parent-party relations, gendered composition of membership and leadership, intensity of campaign labour, and the ideological claims circulating through the organization. Democratic masculinities become more likely when socialization teaches care, accountability, listening, pluralism, and shared responsibility as signs of political seriousness. Anti-democratic masculinities become more likely when socialization rewards hierarchy, exclusion, anti-feminism, leader loyalty, aggression, contempt for compromise, or endurance as the price of belonging.

3.4 CAMPAIGNS, COMMUNICATION, AND LEADERSHIP AS AMPLIFICATION AND TRANSMISSION

Campaigns, communication, and leadership pathways are the points where youth-wing influence becomes visible beyond the organization itself. This section connects directly to the report's broader argument that youth wings can operate as catalyst sites for political masculinities: they do not only recruit, represent, or socialize young people internally; they also help carry gendered political ideas, styles, habits, and actors into public-facing party work. The section asks how youth-wing practices travel through campaign labour, digital communication, candidate pathways, staff roles, and future political careers. The core argument is that these arenas make political masculinities visible, repeatable, and portable. They can amplify democratic masculinities when they reward care, accountability, inclusion, pluralism, and non-violent disagreement, and they can amplify anti-democratic masculinities when they reward hierarchy, aggression, anti-feminism, leader loyalty, exhaustion, or contempt for compromise.

Campaign work offers one of the clearest arenas where youth wings become useful to parent parties. Youth wings often serve as electoral campaigners by canvassing, staffing events, mobilizing young voters, distributing materials, amplifying party messages online, and giving parties a visible youth presence during elections (Bale et al., 2020; Bolin, 2025; de Roon, 2022; Pickard, 2015). Campaigning can provide young members with skills, experience, networks, visibility, and routes into candidate pipelines, while also becoming extractive when parent parties rely on youth-wing energy and unpaid labour without

granting meaningful influence, voice, resources, or internal democracy (Berry, 2008; Bolin & Jungar, 2024).

From the perspective of political masculinities, campaign labour can attach political seriousness to endurance, availability, competitiveness, aggression, care, teamwork, or discipline. A youth wing may teach members that the serious activist is the one who works longest, travels furthest, argues hardest, or defends the party most fiercely. It may also teach members that political commitment means supporting others, sharing labour, managing conflict, and making campaign work sustainable. Campaigns therefore socialize members into gendered expectations of work, commitment, leadership, and loyalty.

Campaigns can also become representational moments. Elections give youth wings visibility and provide opportunities to foreground youth-specific issues, young candidates, or generational claims. In party-list systems, candidate selection and list placement shape which young actors become electorally visible. Youth wings may lobby, nominate, endorse, or mobilize support for young candidates, but senior party selectors often filter these claims through electability, experience, symbolic value, and party strategy (De Smedt & Vandeleene, 2025; Hazan & Rahat, 2010; Jalali et al., 2024). Leadership pathways therefore transmit people and repertoires: ideas about authority, care, loyalty, hierarchy, protection, conflict, and belonging formed or reinforced in youth-wing spaces.

Public and digital communication operate in a comparable way. Youth wings use public statements, social media, memes, campaign videos, podcasts, visual imagery, and platform-specific humour to speak to younger members, parent parties, and broader publics. These tools can make political disagreement more accessible, sharpen critique, and build collective identity. They can also normalize humiliation, anti-feminism, exclusionary humour, or contempt for democratic opponents when communication cultures reward attention over accountability.

Repeated ways of making claims and doing politics become recognizable through performance, gesture, image, speech, emotional tone, and public staging (Moffitt & Tormey, 2014; Tilly, 2006). Youth-wing communication can, therefore, amplify democratic masculinities when it makes care, solidarity, accountability, pluralism, and non-violent disagreement visible as political strengths. It can also amplify anti-democratic masculinities when it normalizes anti-gender humour, grievance, dominance, humiliation, militant aesthetics, contempt for compromise, or fantasies of protection and restored authority. In youth political spaces shaped by humour, speed, irony, and platform culture, the line between playful provocation and exclusionary normalisation may become especially difficult to see.

Leadership development provides the final transmission arena. Youth wings offer structured environments where some young people learn how to move through party organizations, build reputations, gain access to senior actors, and imagine future roles in campaigns, party offices, parliaments, or government. Earlier scholarship emphasized youth wings' role in recruiting and training future political personnel, while more recent studies show that youth-wing participation can shape ambition, career expectations, candidate pathways, and access to party networks (Ammassari et al., 2023; Jalali et al., 2025; Ohmura et al., 2018). Leadership pathways matter for masculinities because they shape which forms of political conduct receive movement, visibility, and institutional access.

Campaigns, communication, and leadership pathways become catalyst mechanisms when they amplify and transmit what youth wings mobilize, authorize, and socialize. They make political masculinities visible in public practice and portable across settings. A caring organizer can become a model of democratic leadership, a combative debate style can become a marker of political seriousness, a joke can become a shared repertoire, a protection claim can become a policy frame, and a campaign aesthetic can make toughness, discipline, grievance, or solidarity feel politically attractive. Youth wings therefore help decide which political masculinities travel with young people into party politics.

4. YOUTH WINGS BETWEEN NORMALIZATION AND MAINSTREAMING

Section 3 showed that youth wings can mobilize young actors, authorize youth-coded claims, socialize political conduct, and amplify ideas, styles, and practices through campaigns, communication, and leadership pathways. Section 4 turns to the report's broader catalyst-site argument: how these youth-wing roles may help democratic or anti-democratic political masculinities become more familiar, legitimate, repeatable, or politically usable beyond the youth wing itself.

The section asks how gendered political ideas and styles move between youth social worlds, youth-wing organizations, parent parties, and public politics. Youth wings matter here because they occupy an intermediate position: close to peer groups, digital cultures, activist scenes, schools, universities, workplaces, and local communities, while also connected to party congresses, campaign teams, candidate pathways, leadership networks, and public communication. This position allows youth wings to concentrate, translate, test, contest, amplify, or contain political masculinities before some of them move further into party politics.

The democratic and anti-democratic pathways are not the same process, even when they travel through similar organizational channels. Democratic masculinities become more likely when youth wings make care, equality, accountability, pluralism, non-violent disagreement, and shared responsibility visible and credible within party life. Anti-democratic masculinities become more likely when youth wings make hierarchy, exclusion, anti-feminism, grievance, leader loyalty, aggressive political style, or contempt for democratic constraint appear normal, useful, or representative of young people. The analytical task is therefore to identify not only whether youth-wing practices travel, but what travels, how it changes form, who authorizes it, and how parent parties respond.

4.1 YOUTH WINGS AS INTERMEDIARY ORGANIZATIONS

Youth wings operate as intermediary organizations because they connect young people's everyday social worlds to formal party structures. This is not the same as the report's catalyst-site claim. Intermediary status describes where youth wings are in party politics whereas catalyst site describes what that position can do. Because youth wings sit between peer groups, digital cultures, activist scenes, schools, universities, workplaces, and parent-party arenas, they can translate ideas, styles, claims, and practices between youth social worlds and institutional politics. They connect young people's everyday social worlds to party structures at a stage when political identities, loyalties, repertoires, and ambitions

are still being formed (Dinas, 2010). This gives them a distinctive place in the wider ecology of democratic and anti-democratic masculinities. They offer practical answers to questions that matter for democratic politics: who belongs, who leads, who receives protection, who becomes a target of ridicule, who speaks with authority, who performs care, and what kinds of conflict count as legitimate.

This position fits the meso-level understanding of socialization developed in work on democratic and anti-democratic masculinities within MEN4DEM. Tomatis and Lomazzi (2025) emphasize that gendered and democratic norms are learned across micro-, meso-, and macro-settings, including peer relations, organizations, and broader political contexts. Youth wings operate in the middle of this process. National party systems, gender regimes, digital cultures, and parent-party expectations shape them, while youth wings create their own routines, hierarchies, jokes, symbols, loyalties, and forms of recognition. Their internal life can therefore give political masculinities a space within their organizations: members hear claims about authority, care, protection, equality, or grievance and learn how those claims are practised in meetings, campaigns, leadership contests, online communication, and relations with senior party actors.

This intermediary role also helps explain why youth wings can be politically consequential despite small membership bases. They do not need to represent most young people to matter, since they bring selected young actors into dense party-linked networks and give some of them access to public communication, campaign roles, candidate pathways, policy debates, and parent-party actors. Their influence often works indirectly, but indirect influence still matters when it shapes political formation, public style, and the movement of repertoires across youth and party spaces.

4.2 WHAT MAY MOVE: IDEAS, STYLES, EMOTIONS, AND PRACTICES

Political masculinities rarely move as explicit statements about men or gender alone. They travel through ideas, styles, emotions, and practices. Ideas include claims about feminism, family, sexuality, migration, nation, security, gender equality, care, protection, and male grievance. Styles refer to how politics is performed: through care, listening, accountability, discipline, provocation, aggression, humour, toughness, or contempt. Emotions include resentment, humiliation, pride, fear, solidarity, hope, wounded status, or the promise of restored authority. Practices include campaigning, mentoring, joking, excluding, caring, disciplining, tolerating harassment, managing conflict, and deciding whose labour or risk is taken for granted (Machado et al., 2024; Machado et al., 2023; McSwiney & Vaughan, 2024).

The manosphere and manfluencer literature helps specify the wider digital environment in which some of these scripts circulate. Ging (2019) shows how online anti-feminist spaces made grievance, woundedness, entitlement, and anti-feminism more mobile and adaptable through Red Pill narratives, anonymity, emotional storytelling, and cross-platform circulation. Gerrand et al. (2025) describe a newer digital ecology in which misogynist content mixes with influencer culture, monetized self-improvement, wellness, neo-stoicism, anti-feminism, conspiracy claims, and reactionary politics (Gerrand et al. 2025). Botto and Gottzén (2024) show how vulnerability, loneliness, dating failure, humiliation, and masculine inadequacy can become routes into red-pill spaces, while Andersen's (2025) work on digital drift cautions against treating participation in incel spaces as uniform or irreversible.

Other work clarifies how grievance can become politically meaningful. Tähkä and Brunila (2025) show how young men's mental health discourse can become entangled with anti-feminist resentment when public language about vulnerability is read as feminized, feminist, or inattentive to men's suffering. Johansson Wilén (2025) shows how incel communities can turn claims of marginality and experience into claims of privileged knowledge, separating those who supposedly understand gendered reality from those cast as duped, privileged, or hostile outsiders. These studies do not provide evidence about youth wings themselves, yet they help identify the kinds of claims, emotional tones, and authority moves that may already be familiar in young people's wider digital and peer worlds.

Democratic alternatives need the same analytical visibility. Research on caring and democratic masculinities shows how care, accountability, non-domination, equality, and shared responsibility can become public and political practices rather than private virtues (Prattes et al., 2025; Wojnicka & de Boise, 2025). Youth wings can make such practices visible and repeatable when they reward accountable leadership, inclusive debate, solidarity, member support, and non-violent disagreement. They can also make anti-democratic masculinities more portable when aggression, grievance, harassment tolerance, anti-gender humour, protectionist hierarchy, or leader loyalty become part of ordinary organizational conduct.

4.3 BETWEEN NORMALIZATION AND MAINSTREAMING

The distinction between normalisation and mainstreaming clarifies the democratic stakes of youth-wing activity. Heinze and Off (2026) define normalisation as a broader process through which stigma erodes, and ideas, actors, styles, or practices become more socially acceptable. Mainstreaming refers more specifically to the uptake, accommodation, or

legitimation of previously niche or radical positions by mainstream political actors. Youth wings may sit between these processes because they are close to social settings where ideas and styles become familiar, humorous, repeated, or emotionally charged, and close to party settings where some of them may become politically useful.

This intermediate position shapes democratic and anti-democratic masculinities. Democratic ways of doing politics may be normalised in youth or civil society spaces before becoming party-facing claims: care-oriented leadership, youth participation, climate justice, anti-violence work, gender equality, pluralism, or democratic accountability. Youth wings can help translate these practices into motions, campaign messages, candidate support, training practices, or parent-party pressure. Anti-democratic ideas and styles may travel in comparable ways, although with different content and democratic consequences: anti-gender claims, masculinist grievance, nationalist protection, humiliation-based humour, authoritarian understandings of order, or styles of conflict that frame democratic constraint as weakness.

Youth wings mediate rather than originate every idea or style they carry. A youth wing may encounter a claim already circulating online, hear it repeated in peer talk, see it made attractive by influencers, adapt it to youth communication, test it in campaign settings, or translate it into arguments about policy, identity, freedom, protection, or generational voice. It may also reject, ridicule, discipline, or replace those scripts with democratic alternatives.

4.4 PARENT PARTIES AS FILTERS, AMPLIFIERS, AND SHIELDS

Youth wings do not mainstream political masculinities on their own. Parent parties shape whether youth-wing repertoires travel further by adopting, softening, ignoring, disciplining, instrumentalizing, or distancing themselves from them when they become publicly costly. This makes parent-party response central to the catalyst-site model. A youth wing may formulate a claim, test a style, or normalize a mode of internal conduct, but its wider political significance depends on whether senior party actors provide access, silence, resources, sanction, containment, or legitimacy.

The youth-wing literature already points to this relational dynamic. Youth-wing members may understand their organizations as vehicles for influencing parent parties, while parent parties may treat youth wings as sources of campaign labour, renewal, ideological pressure, policy innovation, or reputational risk (Bolin, 2025; Fjellman & Rosén Sundström, 2021; Seeberg, 2025). Candidate pathways show the same filtering process. Youth wings can expand the pool of young activists and potential candidates, but senior party selectors

often control nomination procedures, list placement, and access to electable positions (Jalali et al., 2024; Kurz & Ettensperger, 2024). Parent parties therefore determine whether youth-wing repertoires remain marginal, become symbolically useful, enter policy debates, shape campaign style, or move into positions of formal authority.

This filtering role is especially relevant for anti-democratic masculinities. Parent parties may discipline youth-wing actors who cross democratic boundaries, yet they may also benefit from youthful provocation while avoiding full responsibility for it. A youth wing can energize activists, reach radicalized or disaffected constituencies, test provocative messages, or perform a sharper political style while the parent party maintains ambiguity. Silence, weak oversight, fragmented authority, internal factionalism, and electoral calculation can all allow ideas and styles to travel.

Parent parties can also amplify democratic masculinities. They can reward youth-wing practices that model accountability, care, gender equality, democratic disagreement, and inclusive leadership. They can open candidate pathways to young people whose authority does not depend on domination or aggression. They can respond seriously to youth-wing claims without reducing youth wings to campaign machines, require safeguarding, address harassment, support internal democracy, and treat care-oriented political practice as part of democratic leadership.

Youth wings therefore stand in a conditional relationship to mainstream politics. They can help move democratic masculinities toward party recognition, and they can also provide routes through which anti-democratic masculinities gain visibility, legitimacy, and access. The question concerns how their repertoires travel, how they change form, who authorizes them, and how parent parties respond when those repertoires approach the mainstream.

5. CONDITIONS AND POINTS FOR INTERVENTION

The catalyst-site framework helps to identify where democratic capacity can be strengthened and where anti-democratic masculinities may be interrupted. The recommendations below are organized around four intervention points, each directed at an audience:

- Accountability, for parent party actors: support youth wing autonomy while setting clear democratic boundaries around harassment, discrimination, intimidation, anti-democratic rhetoric, and political violence.
- Safeguarding, for youth wing leaders: protect members' well-being and ensure safe, respectful participation through clear reporting channels, conflict procedures, anti-harassment norms, and care-oriented leadership.
- Inclusion, for organizations that collaborate with political parties, including trainers and oversight bodies: widen access to youth wing participation and leadership pathways, especially for young people who are less likely to be recruited, recognized, or supported.
- Communication, for youth wing leadership and parent party campaign teams: make campaign work and digital communication democratic, sustainable, and accountable rather than extractive, abusive, or built around constant availability.

Together these interventions aim to address the conditions under which youth wings cultivate democratic masculinities grounded in care, equality, accountability, pluralism, and non-violent disagreement, or reproduce anti-democratic masculinities organized around hierarchy, exclusion, anti-feminism, aggression, and contempt for democratic constraint.

5.1 ACCOUNTABILITY MECHANISMS

Recommendation: Parent-party leaders, party executives, candidate selectors, campaign managers, and party staff should support youth wing autonomy while setting clear democratic boundaries.

Youth wings need enough autonomy to represent young people, develop their political voice, and challenge parent parties. At the same time, parent parties need to have clear accountability mechanisms when youth wing practices become exclusionary, aggressive, or anti-democratic. The review demonstrates that youth wings often occupy an ambivalent position; while formally attached to the parent party, they may also claim space to innovate, dissent, radicalize, pressure, or speak in a sharper political style.

To those ends, parent parties should treat youth wings as democratic spaces, not only as campaign labor or recruitment pools. Evidence from Seeberg (2025) highlights that parent parties may listen to youth when they make competence-based, or ideologically distinctive arguments. This finding demonstrates that parent party responsiveness matters whether youth wing claims gain legitimacy. Heinze's (2025) study of the Young Alternative for Germany shows us the risk side: political parties may benefit from youth-wing mobilization and ideological energy while simultaneously distancing themselves when youth wing radicalization creates reputational costs. Taken together, these findings highlight the need for parent parties to protect youth wing voice, but to set clear boundaries around harassment, discrimination, intimidation, anti-democratic rhetoric, and political violence.

5.2 SAFEGUARDING: ENSURING SAFE, RESPECTFUL PARTICIPATION

Recommendation: Youth wing chairs, boards, local branch leaders, safety officers, training teams, and youth wing members should work to implement, or maintain internal democracy, safeguarding measures, and democratic conflict norms into everyday organizational life.

For youth wing leaders, branch chairs, safeguarding contacts/intra-party bodies, and party trainers, the core recommendation is to treat internal culture as democratic political training. Youth wings socialize young members through meetings, debates, leadership contests, campaigns, group chats, social events, and informal friendships teach young people what politics rewards. Internal democracy therefore provides a central condition for democratic masculinities. When members can deliberate, dissent, contest leadership, access information, and participate meaningfully in decision-making, youth wings can cultivate political confidence without domination and disagreement without dehumanization. When power becomes concentrated, opaque, personalized, or factionalized, youth wings may teach young members that politics belongs to those who can endure pressure, perform loyalty, and win status through conflict.

Safeguarding and conflict norms should sit at the center of youth-wing leadership practice. Youth political spaces often rely on dense friendship networks, unpaid labor, social events, travel, late-night campaigning, hierarchical mentoring, and informal access to senior actors. These practices can create belonging and solidarity, while also blurring boundaries, intensifying pressure, and making harassment, ridicule, exclusion, or exploitative labor harder to challenge. Research on party organization and toxic masculinity shows that formal rules rarely capture the informal cultures through which gendered power operates inside parties (Daddow & Hertner, 2021). Youth wings require particular attention because younger members may have fewer resources, less status, less

knowledge of party procedures, and stronger incentives to stay silent if they fear losing access.

Youth wing leaders should make care, accountability, and conflict management recognizable political skills. This includes developing, maintaining, and/or implementing clear reporting channels, transparent intra-party procedures, trained safeguarding contacts, anti-harassment norms, and leadership practices that protect members who raise concerns. It also requires everyday cultural work including continuing to challenge jokes that normalize humiliation, the refusal to equate aggression with competence, the recognition of care work as political labor, and the ability to make room for members who participate without adopting combative or masculinized styles of engagement and debate.

Parent parties and organizations that train and support youth wings should resource this work rather than leaving it to individual youth wing leaders. Democratic politics requires disagreement, and youth wings can teach members to make disagreement compatible with pluralism, dignity, and accountability. Intra-party and externally resourced leadership training should therefore include conflict facilitation, bystander intervention, safeguarding measures/tools, inclusive chairing styles, harassment prevention strategies, digital conduct training, and care ethics.

5.3 INCLUSIVE MOBILIZATION AND LEADERSHIP PATHWAYS

Recommendation: Organizations that train or support political parties and youth wings, together with national youth wing oversight, funding, or umbrella bodies, should widen access and strengthen inclusive leadership pathways.

Mobilization determines who enters youth-wing spaces, while leadership pathways determine who gains recognition, influence, and institutional access. The review shows that youth-wing membership is often socially selective, with members more likely to be politically interested, highly educated, civically active, and, in several studies, male (Alarcón-González, 2017; McDonnell et al., 2025; Recchi, 1999). This selectivity makes youth wings especially important as early sites where opportunity, recognition, and political authority are distributed.

Youth wing leaders and parent-party recruitment teams should examine who receives invitations, who feels welcome, and which appeals make participation in the organization meaningful. Youth wings may attract young people through claims for care, equality, climate justice, solidarity, public service, and democratic voice, or/simultaneously through grievance, anti-establishment rebellion, nationalist protection, anti-feminist, or combative peer belonging. Inclusive mobilization means asking whether youth wings reach beyond

already well-connected, urban, highly educated, or male dominated activist circles, and whether their internal cultures facilitate the participation of young people with different resources, backgrounds, and political styles.

Parent parties and candidate selectors should examine what kinds of young political actors their pathways reward. Youth wings can open routes into party office, campaign roles, staff positions, public communications opportunities, candidacy, and elected office. These pathways can cultivate democratic masculinities when they recognize coalition-building, mentoring, conflict mediation, accountability, and inclusive public communication as politically valuable. At the same time, when advancement depends on endurance, insider loyalty, factional aggression, constant availability, or the ability to perform dominance, these pathways can reproduce anti-democratic forms of masculinity.

Organizations that train or support political parties and youth wings should therefore help to make inclusion practical. Training should address inclusive recruitment, mentoring, accessibility, gendered participation barriers, anti-harassment norms, sustainable activism, and leadership styles that do not equate confidence with combativeness. National youth wing oversight, funding, or umbrella bodies can reinforce this work by encouraging basic data collection on membership, leadership retention, safeguarding, and participation. Oversight should not take control over youth wing debate, but should strengthen democratic capacity, transparency, safety, and accountability.

5.4 CAMPAIGN AND DIGITAL COMMUNICATION CULTURES

Recommendation: Youth wing communication teams, campaign managers, social media teams, parent-party communication staff, and organizations that train young political communicators should make campaign and digital communication cultures democratic, sustainable, and accountable.

Campaigns and digital communication spaces are where youth wing norms become public. These sites teach young members how to speak to citizens, handle disagreement, perform loyalty, use humor, represent the party, and claim political authority. To those ends, youth wing and parent party campaign teams should make campaign expectations explicit, fair, and sustainable. Campaign work can build democratic skills when young members learn public explanation, active listening, teamwork, and responsibility to citizens (Malafaia et al. 2018). It can also become extractive when young members are treated mainly as unpaid labor or expected to prove commitments to their party through exhaustion and constant availability. Berry's (2008) analysis of the Young Labour in the UK demonstrates how weak resources and limited internal democracy can undermine youth sections, while Bolin and

Jungar (2024) demonstrate that youth-wing members may value the community and influence they get from their youth wing, but criticize parent party expectations around campaigning, workload, careerism, and conflict.

To those ends, parent party campaign staff should avoid using youth wings as reserve of flexible labor without voice, resources, or influence. Young members should receive meaningful political roles, not only visibility and logistical tasks. Campaign teams should distribute work fairly, protect rest, recognize care work, and make it possible to participate in youth wing life without adopting masculinized expectations of toughness, total availability, or aggressive competitiveness.

Youth wing communications teams and party trainers should also treat digital communication as democratic practice. Youth wings use social media to circulate slogans, campaign images, event reports, candidate promotion, and youth claims. In their two studies Machado et al. (2023, 2024) show that youth wing social media may be used to promote more visibility, document campaigns, and signal through messaging, more than being used for dialogue or engagement with others. This means that digital communications can make young actors and claims visible, but can normalize one-way messaging, ridicule, harassment, anti-feminist provocation, or contempt for opponents.

Youth wings should therefore develop clear norms for online campaigning that include discussions of how to disagree, how to engage with the public, and when and how to use humor. These norms should promote and support communication styles that are sharp without being abusive, persuasive without being dehumanizing, and politically confident without drawing on domination. To those ends, digital and campaign training should include harassment prevention, platform-specific risk assessments, bystander intervention, inclusive messaging styles, and how to democratically disagree.

6. CONCLUSION

Political party youth wings matter for democratic politics because they stand close to both youth social worlds and formal party power. They do not reach all young people or represent youth as a broad demographic category. Rather, their influence lies in the way they bring selected young actors into party-linked spaces, give some youth-coded claims organizational voice, teach members how politics is practiced, and create routes through which political ideas, styles, emotions, and practices may travel into campaigns, parent parties, public communication, staff roles, candidacies, and elected office.

This report has analyzed the role and influence of youth wings and argued that their ordinary party functions make them possible catalyst sites for both democratic and anti-democratic masculinities. Youth wings mobilize, represent, socialize, campaign, communicate, and create leadership pathways. Through these activities, young people learn what kinds of authority, belonging, conflict, care, hierarchy, loyalty, protection, grievance, and democratic participation count as credible politics. Masculinities appear here through explicit claims about men and gender, as well as through everyday practices within these organizations. Who gets invited? Who speaks with authority? Who gains status through loyalty or aggression? Who performs care work? Who receives promotion? Whose discomfort is ignored?

Youth wings can support democratic masculinities when they make care, accountability, pluralism, solidarity, non-violent disagreement, and inclusive participation a part of political training. Campaign work can teach young members to speak with citizens, active listening skills, how to explain party positions, and to treat public engagement as a democratic responsibility. Youth wings can also pressure parent parties on climate, equality, representation, and youth access, as well as open leadership pathways that champion mentoring, coalition-building, conflict mediation, and care-oriented organizing. These practices help to link political strength to values of accountability and shared responsibility.

Youth wings can also promote or reproduce anti-democratic masculinities when they normalize hierarchy, grievance, anti-feminism, aggression, tolerance for violence and harassment, or contempt for democratic constraint. Campaign cultures may reward exhaustion and constant availability, and internal status may depend on factional aggression or insider loyalty. Online communication may reward ridicule, humiliation, and dehumanization. Additionally, parent parties may use youth wings to test more radical claims that they want to accommodate, soften, use strategically, or even publicly disown.

The Young Alternative for Germany, as outlined by Henize (2025) illustrates this risk: youth wing radicalization can generate pressure, networks, and ideological energy for parent parties while creating reputational and democratic costs for itself and the broader political system.

Youth wings are neither the origin of anti-democratic politics, nor sites where violent masculinities can be presumed. They merit attention as party-linked arenas where youth cultures, digital practices, peer recognition, campaign work, and pathways into political careers converge. Their influence operates both directly, through pressure on parent parties over policy and representation, as well as indirectly, as young actors carry styles of debate, humor, care, grievance, leadership, and belonging into wide political party life.

Parent parties shape whether and how youth wing ideas, styles, and practices travel further into formalized politics. Youth wings may test claims, develop leadership skills and styles, and socialize young activists, but parent parties decide whether these practices gain resources, visibility, candidate access, campaign roles, policy attention, or public legitimacy. Parent parties may adopt, soften, ignore, discipline, instrumentalize, or disown what youth wings rehearse. Political parties that treat youth wings mainly as labor miss their democratic significance, while parties that tolerate harmful youth wing conduct because it appears energetic, humorous, loyal, or electorally useful risk giving anti-democratic masculinities legitimacy under the guise of youth politics.

The key takeaway of this report is concrete. Youth wings strengthen democracy when they help young people learn care, accountability, pluralism, voice, and non-violent disagreement as a part of political life. They weaken democracy when they normalize rigid hierarchies, exclusionary practices, hostility toward gender equality, confrontational behavior, and disregard for democratic limits. Parent parties, youth wing leaders, party trainers, and oversight bodies can shape which path becomes more likely by strengthening accountability, safeguarding practices, inclusive leadership pathways, and democratic campaign and digital communication cultures. Youth wings may be small organizations within formal party politics, but they have lasting effects on what young political actors learn to admire, tolerate, and carry forward.

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